

MOULD CASTING OF ALUMINIUM MATRIX HETEROPHASE COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Matrix composites of aluminum alloys (AlMMC) are a new group of engineering materials, which allow not only the replacement of existing materials, but also to create new solutions. They can be used as a suitable lightweight and high abrasion resistance material in place of cast iron and steel in structural elements. Another application of aluminium matrix composites is in the electronics industry, where the low coefficient of thermal expansion is used in radiators [1-6].

Industrial production method of composite elements are mainly based on pressure infiltration process of ceramic inserts. This allows to obtain a locally reinforced material layer with improved characteristics. Technologies such as high pressure die casting or squeeze casting use mainly in high volume production.

Small batch or even unit's production is more profitable base on casting technologies. Preparation of composite suspension by mechanical mixing can take full advantage of opportunities to develop parts in the gravity and centrifugal casting. The paper will be presented the results of research regarding assessment of filling the mold cavity during the casting of the composite suspension.

2 Materials and experimental procedure

Composite materials was prepared according the procedure described in [7]. As the base of matrix alloy was applied AlSi7Mg alloy. Composite suspension was obtained by introducing the SiC and SiC+Cg particles to the liquid metal. To assess the ability to fill the mold cavity was used permanent mold were the getting system can shape the two plates with the dimensions 40 x 80 x 3 mm. Design of getting system allows assessment of the impact of the metalostatic pressure on the shape of casting plates. Mould was equipped with system of electric

heaters provide constant temperature of during casting (300°C). Additionally the measuring system was composed with a ceramic crucible with 20 mm diameter tapping in the bottom and the plug. The temperature of the liquid composite suspension during casting was controlled by type K thermocouple mounted in the plug (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Permanent mould with ceramic crucible.

For the composite materials were made series of three casting with the temperature of the mold filling respectively, 720°C, 700°C and 680°C. Figure 2 shows the mould getting system and the sample cast of composite plates.

Fig. 2. Getting system of the mould and the cast sample.

Shapes of cast composite plates were compared to the plates of cast made by base matrix alloy. The presence of ceramic particles in the suspension significantly change the ability of the material to fill the mold. However, by proper selection of the phase composition of the composite and proper casting parameters give possibility to shape the cast in the mould.

3 Summary

The presented method of testing the ability of the material to fill the mold cavity is comparative in nature. The main goal of the study was to compare the ability of the shaping of the cast (plates) by gravity mould casting the composite suspensions. The next stage of research will be analyze of the structure the plates mainly from the point of distribution in the reinforcement particles in cast.

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